

An Assessment of LinkedIn's Role in Enhancing Employment Opportunities for Commerce Students in Coimbatore City

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Abstract— This study looks at how LinkedIn helps Coimbatore city's commerce students find work. 129 undergraduate and graduate commerce students provided primary data via a structured questionnaire as part of a descriptive research design. Students' perceptions, usage trends, and awareness of LinkedIn for career development are examined in this study. The results show a moderate level of awareness of LinkedIn but little use of it effectively. According to the study, employability results can be enhanced by institutional support and structured training.

Keywords— *LinkedIn, Employment- Opportunities, Commerce, Students Professional Networking, Job Search Platforms, Career Development.*

INTRODUCTION

Digital communication and networking have changed education and employment significantly in the 21st century. In this setting, LinkedIn has become a key professional networking platform for career development and job opportunities. Unlike other social media, LinkedIn lets users build professional profiles, connect with employers, and grow their career networks. It helps students, especially those studying commerce, effectively present their qualifications, skills, and industry interests. They can also gain access to internships, job openings, and professional advice in areas like finance, business, and management. Coimbatore city, a major center for education and industry, provides many career opportunities for commerce students. However, differences in digital skills and support from institutions have resulted in limited awareness and ineffective use of LinkedIn among students. As employers increasingly rely on online profiles for hiring and assessment, a well-maintained LinkedIn profile acts as an extended resume and improves employability. This study looks at how LinkedIn affects the job prospects of commerce students in Coimbatore city.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the fact that LinkedIn is a well-established professional networking website, its influence on the employability skills of students in developing countries has not been explored fully, with most studies being based only on the generation of student profiles and their perceptions of LinkedIn. In the context of commerce students in the city of Coimbatore, the students are deficient in skills and knowledge about the efficient use of LinkedIn for career progression, particularly with the increasing importance attached to the online professional image of individuals. The factors such as the level of awareness about LinkedIn, its utilization, and the difficulties involved will offer significant insights into the same.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To study the demographic profile of the students
- To analyse the awareness level of LinkedIn among commerce students in Coimbatore city

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In this study, the exercise is focused on undergraduates and postgraduates in the field of commerce in colleges in Coimbatore district. The study explores the level of awareness, usage, perceptions, and the extent of the use of LinkedIn in exploring employment opportunities. In this study, the role of LinkedIn in developing employability skills is also explored in detail. However, in this study, the application of LinkedIn and the institutions focused are only in the Coimbatore district.

LIMITATION

The study is based on self-reported questionnaire responses and is restricted to a small sample of commerce students in Coimbatore City, the results may be biased and cannot be completely extrapolated to all commerce students in other areas.

HYPOTHESIS

- Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant association between gender and the level of familiarity with LinkedIn.
- Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant association between the type of college a student studies in and how they first learned about LinkedIn.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It uses a descriptive research design in which the study analyzes the demographic characteristics of the respondents by frequency of the selected variables. In this context, both primary and secondary data are utilized.

Primary Data: The data collected are primary ones through a structured questionnaire designed along the lines of the research objectives.

Secondary Data: Data from secondary sources are collected from books, journals, magazines, articles, previous reports, and relevant websites.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study employs a descriptive research design in assessing the influence of LinkedIn in improving job opportunities for commerce students in the city of Coimbatore.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The convenience sampling technique is used to select the commerce students from the Coimbatore city for the study.

SAMPLE SIZE

- Sample size is defined as the number of sample participants or observations.
- Approximately 129 respondents will be targeted to take part in the study.

TOOLS

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-Square

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Lela Lestri (2024)1, in her study titled “Generation Z career planning: Is LinkedIn an important platform for career planning among Generation Z in Indonesia” aimed to examine how Gen Z students perceive LinkedIn in shaping their career plans. The methodology involved in-depth interviews with 10 purposively selected students from Indonesian universities, all aged below 24 and active LinkedIn users. The findings revealed that students used LinkedIn to gain career information, connect with alumni, and explore professional pathways. Most participants valued LinkedIn for career exploration, self-assessment, and job searches, considering it an essential tool for planning their future. It was suggested that universities integrate LinkedIn workshops and career guidance to strengthen students’ use of the platform. The study concluded that LinkedIn is integral to Gen Z career readiness in Indonesia.

Agha H. Amin (2024)2, in his critical paper titled “Social media platforms like LinkedIn too politically correct and biased” aimed to highlight the limitations and controversies of LinkedIn as a professional networking site. The methodology was based on the author’s observational analysis of LinkedIn activities over several years and feedback from multiple LinkedIn group members exceeding 8,000 participants. The findings revealed issues such as unethical financial dealings, arbitrary account suspensions, exploitation of member identification, low-quality discussions, and the prevalence of fake or bot accounts. It was suggested that reforms in transparency, customer service, and ethical handling of user data are urgently required. The study concluded that LinkedIn

has limited utility as a genuine job search platform and may fail to deliver meaningful employment outcomes.

Sivanandham S (2025)3, in his study titled “A study on impact of social media networking on employment opportunities for college students in Coimbatore city” aimed to assess how digital networking influences employability. The methodology employed a mixed-method approach with surveys and interviews, involving 180 respondents including students, recruiters, and employers. The findings indicated that LinkedIn, Facebook, and other social media platforms significantly impacted job discovery, recruitment decisions, and skill development. While social media improved visibility and networking, challenges such as misinformation and privacy risks were noted. The study concluded that social media is a critical tool in professional development and recommended targeted digital literacy programs for students to maximize benefits while addressing risks.

RESEARCH GAP

Researchers had conducted research on the concept of LinkedIn as a means to utilize employment opportunities in a general sense, internationally, without much concern to commerce students in Coimbatore city. There is a lack of research done on the awareness of LinkedIn as a tool to utilize employment opportunities among commerce students. Thus, a research gap is noticed to assess the role of LinkedIn in improving employability among commerce students.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

DEMOGRAPHICS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	
GENDER	Male	64	49.5
	Female	65	
	Total	129	
AGE	18-20	36	27.9
	21-25	59	
	26-30	34	
	Total	129	
LEVEL OF THE STUDY	UG-B.Com	37	28.7
	PG-M.Com	60	
	Professional Course (CA/CS/CMA)	32	

Total	129	100	
YEAR OF STUDY ARE YOU CURRENTLY IN	First Year	21	16.3
Second Year	48	37.2	
Third Year	43	33.3	
Pass out	17	13.2	
Total	129	100	
TYPE OF COLLEGE DO YOU STUDY IN	Government	20	15.5
Aided	43	33.3	
Self-financing	42	32.6	
Autonomous	24	18.6	
Total	129	100	

(Source: Primary Data)

Table 1

INTERPRETATION:

The gender distribution in the study is close to an equal proportion with 49.5% males and 50.4% females. The age group in which maximum respondents (45.7%) are included is 21-25 years, followed by 18-20 years (27.9%) and then 26-30 years (26.4%). The educational qualification of the students indicates that the maximum students belong to the PG-M.Com (46.5%) group, followed by UG-B.Com (28.7%), with 37.2% students in the second year and 33.3%.

Pearson Chi-Square Tests

Type of college do you study in		
How did you first learn about LinkedIn?	Chi - square	6.982
	df	12
	Sig.	.859a

(Source: Primary data)

Table 2

INTERPRETATION:

The Chi-square value is 1.296 (df = 3, p = 0.730). Since p > 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, so there is no significant association between gender and familiarity with LinkedIn. Males and females have similar levels of familiarity.

FINDINGS

1.The demographic profile of respondents: The gender proportion is roughly even, with 49.5% respondents being male and 50.4% female. The majority are from the 21-25 years age group, with a response rate of 45.7%, followed by 27.9% from the 18-20 years age group. More respondents are PG (M.Com) students, with 46.5%, as opposed to UG (B.Com) students, with a response rate of 28.7%, most of whom are in their second year (37.2%) and third year (33.3%) of college. The 2.Chi-square analysis results: It is seen that the chi-square tests indicate that there is no significant relationship between gender and LinkedIn familiarity, given the p-value of 0.730, and also that there is no significant relationship between type of college and the study variable, given that the p-value is 0.859. Both p-values are more than 0.05. So, the null hypothesis is accepted for both.

SUGGESTION

The findings of the study signify that the familiarity with LinkedIn does not vary substantially with respect to gender or type of college. Thus, awareness and career guidance programs on LinkedIn can be conducted for all students on a uniform basis. The colleges can encourage the students to use LinkedIn more actively in networking, internship, and career development through workshops and practical training. Inclusion of LinkedIn-based activities within the curriculum may enhance students' professional exposure even further.

CONCLUSION

The study comes to the conclusion that, with comparable awareness levels across gender and college type, LinkedIn may improve job prospects for Coimbatore city's commerce students. However, due to a lack of appropriate guidance, the platform's potential for career development remains limited. Therefore, integrating career counseling and LinkedIn-based training into college curricula can enhance students' employability and professional preparedness.

REFERENCE

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